

FAIR Samples: exploring research and sample data management best practices in place-based research

The California Digital Library and RSpace

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I. Project Overview

Field stations represent crucial sites where the application of FAIR principles—concepts designed to improve metadata preparation and ensure that research data is both discoverable and interoperable—can significantly impact local communities by advancing research and innovation. These stations are essential for collecting primary data across various disciplines and present a unique opportunity to enhance community development through improved research practices. One of the primary challenges in field-based research is the efficient management of physical samples, which is vital for data integrity and the integration of different data types. Our project has identified significant inefficiencies in how samples are cataloged and managed at these stations, affecting data retention and quality, as well as the integration of sample data with experimental data in adherence to FAIR principles.

The "FAIR Samples" project will explore these issues by developing and iterating strategies that span from policy creation to information dissemination, focusing particularly on enhancing sample management through the RSpace platform. RSpace has recently integrated material sample PIDs into its inventory and sample management system. This integration facilitates the seamless registration, metadata editing, and publishing of IGSN IDs, which are PIDs provided by DataCite for material samples. This feature simplifies the process for users, embedding persistent identification into everyday sample management tasks.

As part of this initiative, we will investigate how a PID-enabled sample management system can work synergistically with other research tools to support comprehensive sample workflows. This includes increasing adherence to FAIR principles, reducing the manual effort required to maintain these practices, and enhancing the overall usability and adoption of these systems.

Adopting a workflow-led, iterative product development approach that incorporates user feedback, the "FAIR Samples" project will aim to improve the management and quality of data at field stations through the following objectives:

- 1. TECHNOLOGICAL: Implement integrations between the RSpace sample management system and research tools that empower key stages of place-based research lifecycles, to enable a comprehensive and integrated field station sample metadata and data flow, from collection to deposit. (Module 1, 3)**
- 2. TECHNOLOGICAL: Develop a proof-of-concept for interconnecting PIDs (IGSN ID, PIDINST, ORCID, ROR) within a research tool, enabling a rich PID graph to be**

generated automatically, in order to facilitate sample relationship and provenance tracking. (Module 2)

3. **TECHNOLOGICAL:** Explore how research tools can enact policy compliance and FAIR practices, and thus facilitate research data management compliance with FAIR policy through interoperable design (Module 1, 2, 3)
4. **SOCIAL:** Draft guidelines for the design and development of end-to-end research tool solutions that support research data management and policy compliance. (Module 3)
5. **SOCIAL:** Provide a practical, working example of an end-to-end solution for field station sample management to support and illustrate the above guidelines through an open development and design process. (Module 3)

II. Project Design

Overview

Figure 1: FAIR Samples Ecosystem

Module 1: Enabling field sample and data capture workflows

Task 1.1 - Integrate RSpace with FieldMark to support offline field data collection: In order to enable offline sample collection during field trips, RSpace will develop an integration with FieldMark, an open source, domain-agnostic mobile field data collection application. FieldMark supports customisable templates for samples and observations, that can be utilized to ensure metadata and policy compliance in the very early stages of sample processing; the sample metadata can then be directly ingested into RSpace. We aim to explore how to preserve the essential metadata granularity when integrating two systems that do not have identical metadata templates, and whether generalization is possible.

Task 1.2 - Support registration, editing, and publishing of PIDINST IDs in RSpace:

PIDINST IDs are designed for persistent identification of research instruments, and map onto the DataCite metadata schema. Instruments, and their resulting measurements, are a core component of sample-centered workflows, and thus need to be FAIR themselves. By integrating PIDINST IDs into RSpace Inventory, we will investigate the similarities and differences in the management of PIDs for instruments in contrast to samples, and the generalisability of domain-specific instrument management.

Task 1.3 - Improve DMP Tool and RSpace integration to facilitate policy compliance

within a research tool: The DMP Tool and RSpace have a history of collaboration, and a pilot integration was developed to enable workflow integration by connecting RSpace, DMP Tool, and data repositories. This tri-directional integration facilitates comprehensive research data capture, tracking, and enhanced data quality. During this proposed project, we will explore opportunities to further advance the integration between DMP Tool and RSpace. We aim to understand how the use of machine-actionable data management plans within an active research tool can facilitate early awareness and compliance with FAIR data policies, particularly regarding the management of samples. To achieve this, we will explore methods of viewing up-to-date versions of DMSPs within RSpace automatically updating these plans with PIDs and referencing various published research outputs, especially IGSN IDs.

Module 2: Enhancing sample provenance, relationships, and tracking

Task 2.1 - Enhancement of sample and instrument relationship modeling within RSpace:

We will incorporate flexible relationship modeling for samples and instruments, in order to support DataCite's related identifier feature. The explicit description of the relationships that samples and instruments can have with each other (parent-child, "is part of"-"has part") is paramount to accurate and effective tracking of the sample's lifecycle and understanding its relationship with various instruments, whether in the field or in the lab. What is more, related identifiers are the basis for the generation of PID graphs, which enable both internal and external tracking and communication about outputs across the research lifecycle.

Task 2.2 - Linking ORCID IDs and RORs with outputs for enhanced collaboration and

funder tracking: In order to efficiently record and track the research associated with a specific funder or individual, there is a need to both ensure PIDs referencing these entities are consistently recorded, and carried over as related identifiers of the research outputs that are produced. We will explore how a sample management system integrated with a lab notebook can centralize this work and automatically populate a research output's metadata with collaborator and funder PIDs, based on existing knowledge available in the system.

Task 2.3 - Explore support for domain-specific sample and subsample concepts for richer

workflow support: A "sample" at a field station can take on many forms, from a sediment sample to an anthropological data point. A sample management system needs to reflect this complexity, and provide enough flexibility that accurate sample representations and relationships can be modeled. Otherwise, the resulting metadata will carry assumptions that are not suited for that particular domain sample, and result in erroneous interpretation. We wish to

specifically extend the “sample”/“subsample” model currently in place in RSpace Inventory, for example by providing support for a singleton sample construct.

Task 2.4 Automatic PID Graph generation for sample workflows: The FAIR Island report (Robinson et al., 2022) describes the generation of a graph that enables tracking relationships between researchers, outputs, funders, DMPs, and various other entities including samples and related instruments. We aim to generate a PID graph demonstrating the sample flow from collection to repository deposit, utilizing the research tool and PID integrations to explore automatic generation of this graph for an example field station project.

Module 3: Supporting research data management with FAIR policy compliance

Task 3.1 - Enhance existing deposits by populating metadata with related IGSN IDs: In order to complete the end-to-end sample workflow, samples should be discoverable when accessing a project’s research outputs, as deposited in a repository such as Dataverse and Zenodo. To achieve this aim, we will implement support for the automatic association of IGSN IDs with a Dataverse deposit, when the deposit contains research materials that reference samples with IGSN IDs in RSpace. This work will involve a close collaboration with Dataverse and Zenodo to then display the sample metadata on a deposit’s landing page, which will inform our understanding of how to effectively reference PIDs across research tools.

Task 3.2 - Enable a Data Manager role and functionality to support researchers in FAIR compliance: To facilitate the adoption, maintainability, and administration of the features described across all three Modules, we will design a new user role in RSpace, the Data Manager. This role is explicitly focused specifically on ensuring policy compliance, supporting researchers, and serving as a quality touchpoint for data FAIRness. This can take the shape of repository deposit review, project DMP management, and metadata templating. The implementation process will broaden our understanding of how research tools can best support research data managers in their work.

Task 3.3 - Provide guidelines on designing FAIR end-to-end sample workflows in research tools: We will summarize our learnings from the various design, implementation and collaboration work outlined above into practical guidelines, and provide the research data management community with a concrete demonstration of how FAIR data policy can be enabled by research tools and specific features therein.

III. Rationale & Outcomes

This project leverages an iterative design process aimed at developing a deep understanding of the practical needs for vertical interoperability among research tools across the entire research lifecycle. Such interoperability is crucial for ensuring that research data management systems like RSpace can effectively interact with other tools and platforms, a topic that remains largely unexplored, especially within the specific context of field station workflows.

By focusing on the distinct environment of field stations and building upon existing interoperability frameworks within RSpace, this project is poised to significantly advance our knowledge of how interoperability can be practically implemented and how it can enhance the adoption of FAIR principles in research workflows. This focus on practical application is particularly suited to the EAGER funding mechanism, which supports projects with potential for profoundly transformative outcomes.

Expected outcomes include:

1. **An end-to-end sample management solution for field stations**, that brings together FieldMark, RSpace, DMP Tool and data repositories (Dataverse, Zenodo) into a unified workflow
2. **Proof-of-concept of automatic PID graph generation** enabled by IGSN ID, PIDINST, ORCID and ROR linkage and implementation in RSpace, as well as sample relationship modeling, assisting research data managers with provenance tracking and funder communications
3. **Guidelines on designing FAIR sample workflows in research tools**, alongside multiple reports and published findings outlining the project design approach and learnings
4. **Ongoing contributions to the global conversation on research tool needs for research data management**, through regular involvement with research data management communities and tools (RDA, Dataverse, IGSN ID e.V.) to present and share our outputs and findings in a transparent manner, and ensure adoption of best practises by the wider research community

IV. Broader Impacts

The "FAIR Samples" project situates itself at the vital confluence of research and societal needs, particularly within the unique environments of field stations. Implementing FAIR principles in these settings is crucial not only for enhancing data management but also for fostering significant societal benefits. By establishing optimized FAIR workflows at field stations, this project is poised to directly benefit local communities by integrating advanced scientific methodologies into community-oriented research efforts. These enhancements will serve as exemplary best practices for a wide array of research domains, demonstrating the tangible benefits of integrating FAIR principles into diverse research environments.

In addition, this project stands to contribute valuable case studies to the infrastructure of scientific research, showcasing the practical applications of theoretical frameworks. By centering on tangible implementations of FAIR workflows, the project will enable in-depth discussions on policy, processes, and interoperability that are deeply rooted in the real-world operations of field stations. Such discussions are aimed at addressing practical bottlenecks in data management processes, thereby improving the efficiency and effectiveness of research practices, which in turn benefits researchers, data managers, and the broader community. This project exemplifies how targeted improvements in research infrastructure can lead to broad societal impacts, enhancing both local and scientific communities.

The enhancements to cataloging and managing samples at field stations that the project will focus on will enable improvements in data retention and quality, the integration of sample data

with experimental data, and FAIR-compliant best practices in research projects carried out in field stations, which as demonstrated in the previously funded FAIR Island project, are an important but under-resourced research infrastructure. Moreover, the enhancements to the RSpace sample management system will be of benefit to researchers incorporating sample management and recording into their experiments more generally, in the many environments where samples are collected, processed and analyzed, e.g., the lab.

We will summarize our learnings from the various design, implementation and collaboration work outlined above into practical guidelines, and provide the research data management community with a concrete demonstration of how FAIR data policy can be enabled by research tools and specific features therein. By generalizing the knowledge gained into a tool and domain agnostic “blueprint” that distills the challenges involved in cross-tool interoperability across the research lifecycle, we aim to contribute an important, practice-driven piece to the global conversation on the design of research data management infrastructures.